

1 **An alternative *in vitro* model considering cell-cell interactions in** 2 **fiber-induced pulmonary fibrosis**

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10 **Abstract**

11 Particularly since the wide-ranging health effects of asbestos exposure became known, great
12 emphasis has been placed on detailed toxicity testing of known but also newly developed fiber
13 materials. Exposure to respirable pollutants like fibers can lead to tissue injury causing lung
14 diseases such as pulmonary fibrosis or cancer. In order to detect the toxic potential of such
15 aerosols at an early stage, the development of suitable test systems is essential. In this study,
16 we illustrate the development of an advanced *in vitro* cell model closely resembling the
17 physiological structure of the alveoli, and we highlight its advantages over simpler models to
18 predict pro-fibrotic changes. For this reason, we analyzed the cytotoxic effects of fiber-like
19 multi-walled carbon nanotubes after 24 and 48 h exposure, and we investigated inflammatory,
20 genotoxic and pro-fibrotic changes occurring in the developed triple culture consisting of lung
21 epithelial cells, macrophages and fibroblasts compared to a co-culture of epithelial cells and
22 fibroblasts or a mono culture of epithelial cells. In summary, the triple culture system is more
23 precisely able to detect a pro-fibrotic phenotype including epithelial-mesenchymal transition
24 as well as secondary genotoxicity, even if exhibiting lower cytotoxicity in contrast to the less
25 advanced systems. These effects might be traced back to the complex interplay between the
26 different cell types, all of which play an important role in the inflammatory response, which
27 precedes wound healing, or even fibrosis or cancer development.

28 29 **Keywords**

30 MWCNTs – oxidative stress – inflammation – secondary genotoxicity – EMT

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36 1. Introduction

37 Since the pronounced toxic effects of asbestos became common knowledge, more and more
38 emphasis has been placed on the toxicological characterization of fiber and fiber-like materials.
39 Respirable fibrous materials can cause acute and chronic inflammation possibly resulting in
40 severe fibrotic changes of the lung tissue and even cancer formation (Robledo and Mossman
41 1999; Donaldson and Seaton 2012). The extent of toxicity depends both on the physical and
42 chemical properties of the fiber (Bernstein et al. 2001), as well as on the complex interaction
43 of cells such as alveolar macrophages (Dorger and Krombach 2002; Schinwald et al. 2012) and
44 fibroblasts (Kendall and Feghali-Bostwick 2014), which are significantly involved in clearance
45 and wound healing processes of the lung. Particularly long and biopersistent fibers may
46 overload and disrupt the latter protective mechanisms (Oberdorster 2002), which can lead to
47 serious damage to the lung and the mesothelium. Especially the so called WHO fibers
48 possessing a length of $> 5 \mu\text{m}$, a diameter $< 3 \mu\text{m}$ and a length-to-diameter ratio > 3 are
49 considered as hazardous, as they are difficult to clear from the lung and can penetrate deeply
50 into the alveolar regions (IARC Monographs - 100C). Upon impact by such fibrous substances,
51 immune cells or fibroblasts are activated, which may cause a release of reactive oxygen species
52 (ROS) as well as inflammatory mediators initiating a signaling cascade to recruit further cells
53 to the site of injured tissue (D'Urso and Kurniawan 2020). An imbalance of these complicated
54 cell-cell interactions can result in increased cytotoxic, pro-fibrotic or genotoxic effects (Yu et
55 al. 2019), which must be taken into consideration for risk assessment of fibrous material.

56 Until a few years ago, the main route to perform such complex investigations, which deal with
57 the interaction of different cell types and the resulting activation of various signaling pathways,
58 was in the animal organism (Vandamme 2015; Meigs et al. 2018). Not only for ethical as well
59 as cost- and time-effective reasons, but also because of differential physiology of animals and
60 humans, it is necessary to develop easy-to-use alternative methods that allow to reduce or even
61 replace animal experiments. Moreover, advanced cell models help to understand how single
62 cell types influence the response of a multicellular system, elucidating mechanisms of action
63 of certain materials. Many toxicological *in vitro* studies dealing with the effects of fiber
64 materials on the pulmonary system often consider the response of a single cell line such as
65 alveolar epithelial cells, macrophages or fibroblasts exclusively (Wang P et al. 2015). Only few
66 take the communication between two (Di Ianni et al. 2021; Friesen et al. 2022), or even three
67 (Barosova, Karakocak, et al. 2020; Barosova, Maione, et al. 2020) different cell types into
68 account, which might result in an over- or underestimation of the outcomes. Furthermore, up
69 to now, studies of multicellular systems mainly focus on the direct effects on epithelial cells,
70 without reflecting secondary effects on other cell types like fibroblasts, which can cause
71 comparably severe, if not even worse, changes to the organ of interest. The aim of this study
72 was to develop a cell model comprising three cell types mostly involved in the response upon
73 exposure to fibers, and to demonstrate the differences in response compared to simpler models
74 involving only one or two cell types. For this reason, we investigated the toxicity of multi-
75 walled carbon nanotubes (MWCNTs), which are known to possess fiber-like properties
76 (Donaldson et al. 2013; Kane et al. 2018), in the developed triple culture system (TC)
77 comprising epithelial cells, macrophages and fibroblasts in comparison to a mono culture (MC)

78 of epithelial cells and a co-culture (CC) of epithelial cells and fibroblasts. In principle, the term
79 co-culture is used for models with more than one cell type. However, in this study, for the sake
80 of simplicity, it is used to refer to the model with specifically two cell types. This study shows
81 the importance to investigate secondary tissue toxicity and highlights the need for more
82 advanced cell systems in order to more closely resemble human physiological conditions.

83

84 **2. Material and methods**

85 **2.1 Physico-chemical characterization of MWCNTs and dispersion in cell culture** 86 **medium**

87 MWCNTs were used as testing material. A high-purity MWCNT powder was purchased from
88 Ossila (M2009D2). The morphology and the average diameter of the dry carbon nanotube
89 powder was analyzed by a field emission scanning electron microscope (ScEM, MERLIN®
90 VP Compact, Co. Zeiss, Oberkochen) equipped with an energy dispersive X-ray (EDX)
91 detector (XFlash 6/30, Co. Bruker, Berlin). Representative areas of the sample were analyzed
92 for elemental composition on basis of the EDX-spectra data by QUANTAX ESPRIT
93 Microanalysis software (version 2.0). The sample was mounted on an Al-ScEM-carrier with
94 adhesive conductive carbon tape (co. PLANO, Wetzlar). ScEM-images were taken from the
95 selected regions (conditions like applied detector, accelerating voltage, working distance are
96 given in the figures). For dispersion preparation, material was weighed into glass vials and
97 suspended in 1 % bovine serum albumine (BSA, biomol, 01400.100) in ultrapure water giving
98 a concentration of 1 mg/mL. Particles were suspended by two cycles of 15 min in an ultrasonic
99 bath (Palssonic, ALLPAX Germany) not exceeding 37 °C and inverting the vial in between
100 cycles. Afterwards, the suspension was diluted with exposure medium (see section 2.2) to a
101 concentration of 0.5 mg/mL. The dilution was suspended in the ultrasonic bath for another 5
102 min, vortexed and immediately added to the cells on transferrable 12 mm Transwell® inserts
103 with a polyester membrane (0.4 µm pore-size, Type #3460, Corning, NY, USA) reaching the
104 respective exposure concentration (0.0, 2.2, 4.5, 11.2 and 22.3 µg/cm²). The particle size of
105 dispersed MWCNTs at the highest concentration in serum-free cell culture medium was
106 determined via dynamic light scattering (DLS; Zetasizer Nano ZS machine, Malvern
107 Instruments Ltd), including the detection of the ζ-potential. To exclude toxic effects from
108 bacterial origin, endotoxin content of the material was analyzed by the Pierce LAL
109 chromogenic endotoxin quantification Kit (Thermo Scientific, 88282, should be replaced by
110 animal origin-free endotoxin tests in the future).

111

112 **2.2 Cell culture and model systems**

113 A549 human alveolar epithelial cells (ATCC®, CCL-185™), THP-1 human monocytic
114 leukaemia cells (ECACC, 88081201) and MRC-5 human fetal lung fibroblast-like cells (kindly
115 provided by Dr. Andreas Moosmann, Helmholtz Zentrum München, Germany) were routinely
116 cultured in high-glucose Gibco Dulbecco's Modified Eagle Medium. This consists of Nutrient
117 Mixture F-12 (DMEM/F-12; LIFE Technologies, 31331093) supplemented with 5 % (v/v) fetal

118 bovine serum (FBS; LIFE Technologies, 10500064), 100 U/mL penicillin, and 100 µg/mL
119 streptomycin (P/S; Sigma-Aldrich, P4333) in a humidified incubator at 37 °C and 5 % CO₂.
120 Culture dishes of MRC-5 cells were coated for one hour with bovine collagen 1 (25 µg/mL,
121 LIFE Technologies, A1064401) at 37 °C.

122 For experiments, on day 1, Transwell® inserts were coated for one hour with bovine collagen
123 1 (25 µg/mL) from both sides at 37 °C and subsequently washed twice with Dulbecco's
124 phosphate-buffered saline (DPBS; LIFE Technologies, 14190094). Afterwards, A549 cells
125 were trypsinized with 0.05 % Trypsin-EDTA solution (Sigma-Aldrich, MFCD00130286) and
126 seeded on top of the membrane at a density of 2.7x10⁴ cells/cm² growth area in 0.5 mL
127 DMEM/F-12 (5 % FBS) (**Fig. 1A, Day 1**). 1.0 mL DMEM/F-12 was added to the basolateral
128 compartment. On the same day, for the triple culture (TC), THP-1 cells were differentiated into
129 macrophages by a treatment with 300 ng/mL phorbol 12-myristate 13-acetate (PMA, Fisher
130 Scientific, 15476069). After 24 h (day 2), the PMA containing medium was removed and
131 differentiated THP-1 cells were washed twice with DPBS and kept in DMEM/F-12
132 supplemented with 5 % FBS for another 24 h. The successful differentiation from monocytes
133 into macrophages was confirmed via CD11b antibody staining (described in section 2.8, **Fig.**
134 **1B**). On day 3, the Transwell® insert was transferred inversely from the well plate to a petri
135 dish. For the co-culture (CC) and the triple culture model MRC-5 cells were trypsinized with
136 0.25 % Trypsin-EDTA solution and seeded in a spiral on the basolateral side of the membrane
137 at a density of 1.8x10⁴ cells/cm² growth area in a 0.2 mL DMEM/F-12 droplet (5 % FBS)
138 allowing attachment for one hour. Afterwards, the Transwell® insert was transferred back to
139 the well plate and for the triple culture differentiated THP-1 cells were trypsinized with 0.25
140 % Trypsin-EDTA solution and seeded at a density of 5.4x10⁴ cells/cm² growth area in 0.5 mL
141 DMEM/F-12 (5 % FBS). The medium in the basolateral compartment was renewed (**Fig. 1A,**
142 **Day 3**). On day 5, cells were treated with different concentrations of MWCNT suspension in
143 0.5 mL serum-free DMEM/F-12 medium supplemented with 1 % P/S in the apical
144 compartment. The medium in the basolateral compartment was renewed with DMEM/F-12
145 containing 5 % FBS (**Fig. 1A, Day 5**). All experiments were conducted with cells seeded after
146 5-10 passages.

147 All model systems were at all times treated in the same way regarding medium changes as well
148 as the inverting of the insert to ensure comparability, even if no cells were added to the mono
149 culture (MC) or co-culture. Cells were then exposed for 24 h or 48 h. After the exposure, the
150 effects of the MWCNT treatment on cells were assessed directly using the assays described
151 below and the exposure medium was collected in aliquots and frozen at -80 °C for later
152 analysis.

153

154

155 **Figure 1:** A) Experimental set-up of the triple culture system comprising alveolar epithelial
 156 cells, fibroblasts and macrophages. Created with BioRender.com and B) immunohistochemical
 157 staining of the triple culture model comprising alveolar epithelial cells (green, phalloidin A488)
 158 and differentiated macrophages (red, CD11b) on the apical side of the membrane (after
 159 washing and fixation) as well as fibroblasts (green, phalloidin A488) on the basolateral side of
 160 the membrane on the day of exposure. Nuclei were stained with DAPI (blue). Scale bar, 100
 161 μm.

162

163 2.3 Cell count and colony forming efficiency (CFE)

164 The cytotoxicity of MWCNTs was assessed by analyzing the colony forming efficiency
 165 including trypan blue (Sigma-Aldrich, 93595) cell count. For this, cells were washed three
 166 times with DPBS immediately after exposure and incubated with 0.25 % Trypsin-EDTA
 167 solution for 4 min at 37 °C in both compartments. Trypsin was inactivated with FBS and cells
 168 of the apical and the basolateral compartment were detached and collected separately. Cells
 169 were centrifuged at 200 g and 4 °C for 7 min. The supernatant was removed and the cell pellet
 170 resuspended in cold DPBS. Live cells were counted manually with trypan blue using a
 171 hemocytometer. Results of the cell count are shown as % cell count + standard error of the
 172 mean (SEM, n=3) compared to the negative control. Aliquots of the cell suspension were
 173 prepared for the CFE as well as the comet assay (described in section 2.6). The CFE assay was
 174 conducted by seeding collected A549 cells at a density of 300 cells per well in 6-well plates
 175 (VWR, 391-8036) in 2 mL medium with 5 % FBS. Medium was changed every 48 to 72 h.
 176 After 9 days, cells were fixed with 3.4 % paraformaldehyde (Carl Roth, 4980.1) in DPBS for
 177 30 minutes and stained with 10 % sterile-filtered Giemsa solution (AppliChem, A0885).
 178 Colonies were counted manually using ImageJ software. Data are presented as % clonogenicity
 179 + SEM (MC/CC/TC (24 h): n = 7, MC/CC (48 h): n = 7, TC (48 h): n=6); average of treatment
 180 colonies divided by the average of negative control colonies multiplied by 100) compared to
 181 the negative control.

182

183 **2.4 Lactate dehydrogenase (LDH) release**

184 Apical and basolateral media directly collected after the treatment were analyzed by the
185 Cytotoxicity Detection Kit^{Plus} (L-LDH; Roche, 11644793001). Serum-free and 5 % FBS
186 containing exposure medium served as blank for the apical and the basolateral compartment,
187 respectively. A 2 % Triton-X (Sigma-Aldrich, X100) solution acted as positive control. The kit
188 was used according to the manufacturer's instructions. The LDH release was assessed by
189 measuring the absorbance at 493 nm with a VarioskanTM LUX multimode microplate reader
190 (Thermo Scientific). Since a leakage of LDH through the membrane of the Transwell[®] insert
191 cannot be excluded, the LDH release into both compartments was summed up. The results are
192 shown as % cytotoxicity + SEM (MC/CC: n=4, TC: n=3).

193

194 **2.5 Liquid chromatography - tandem mass spectrometry (LC-MS/MS): Malondialdehyde** 195 **(MDA) level**

196 The level of oxidative stress after MWCNT treatment was assessed via the lipid peroxidation
197 biomarker malondialdehyde (MDA). MDA concentrations were quantified as previously
198 described (Wu et al. 2017) from the collected sample media by using LC-MS/MS (API 4000
199 Triple Quadrupole system, AB Sciex in positive MRM mode). MDA was derivatized with 2,4-
200 Dinitrophenylhydrazine (DNPH; Sigma-Aldrich, 04732) and subsequently extracted with
201 liquid-liquid extraction followed by chromatographic separation on a C18 column (Agilent
202 1290 UHPLC System) in isocratic conditions. Data are presented as MDA ng/mL + SEM
203 (n=3).

204

205 **2.6 Single cell gel electrophoresis (comet assay)**

206 As a measure of DNA damage, the alkaline version of single cell gel electrophoresis, also
207 known as comet assay, was performed. After exposure, cells were treated as described in
208 section 2.2. From the cell suspension aliquots, the mini-gel version of the comet assay was
209 conducted as previously described (Di Bucchianico et al. 2017). On each slide (pre-coated with
210 0.5 % normal gelling temperature agarose, Sigma-Aldrich, 05066), eight agarose-gels (1 % low
211 gelling temperature agarose, Sigma-Aldrich, A9414) were prepared embedding MWCNTs-
212 treated cells, positive control cells (30 μ M H₂O₂, Merck Millipore 107209, treated cells) as
213 well as untreated negative control cells of A549 and MRC-5 cells (625 cells/gel). Briefly, cells
214 were lysed for 1 h and DNA underwent alkaline unwinding for 40 min with subsequent
215 electrophoretic separation (25 min, 270–300 mA, 1.2 V/cm²). Gels were neutralized using 0.4
216 M TRIS (Carl Roth, Karlsruhe, Germany, A411.1) and washed with ultrapure water. Slides
217 were air-dried and stained with SYBRTM Green I Nucleic Acid Gel Stain (Invitrogen, S7563).
218 Micrographs were taken with the Lionheart FX automated microscope in 20x magnification.
219 100 nucleoids per treatment were scored manually using the CometScore 2.0 (TriTek Corp)
220 software. Results are presented as % DNA in tail + SEM (n=3).

221

222 **2.7 Enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay (ELISA)**

223 The collected sample media were analyzed for cytokine release using DuoSet® ELISA Kits
224 (ELISA, R&D Systems, DY208) for the pro-inflammatory chemokine interleukin 8 (IL-8) and
225 the cytokine transforming growth factor beta (TGF-β). The assay was carried out according to
226 manufacturer's instructions. 3,3',5,5'-tetramethylbenzidine (TMB; Cell Signaling Technology,
227 7004P6) was used as chromogenic substrate and the absorbance was measured at 450 nm and
228 540 nm with the Varioskan™ Lux multimode microplate reader. Results are presented as IL-8
229 and TGF-β pg/mL + SEM (MC/CC: n=5, TC: n=4).

230

231 **2.8 Immunofluorescence**

232 Immunohistochemical staining of monoclonal mouse anti-human antibodies CD11b (1:200,
233 Invitrogen, 14-0118-82), E-cadherin (1:50, CDH1, Biozol, DNA-AB-138269), N-cadherin
234 (1:150, CDH2, OriGene, TA320305), vimentin (VIM, 1:200, Biozol, EXB-11-460-C100) as
235 well as α-smooth muscle actin (α-SMA, 1:200, ACTA2, Invitrogen, MA5-11547) was
236 performed. Membranes of untreated cells on the exposure day of the TC as well as untreated
237 cells and cells treated with the highest MWCNT concentration (22.3 µg/cm²) for 48 h of the
238 TC, CC and MC were analyzed. Following exposure, Transwell® inserts were washed twice
239 with DPBS, fixed with 3.4 % PFA for 30 min at room temperature (RT) and washed with
240 DPBS. Subsequently, cells were scraped from either the apical or the basolateral side of the
241 insert membranes to enable staining of only one side of the insert. The membranes were cut
242 out with a scalpel, turning the inserts containing fibroblasts to stain the basolateral side, before
243 washing with wash buffer containing 0.05 % Tween® 20 in DPBS. Afterwards, membranes
244 were permeabilized by 0.25 % Triton™ X-100 in DPBS for 15 min, followed by another
245 washing step and blocking with blocking buffer consisting of 1 % BSA in DPBS for 30
246 minutes. Cells were incubated with the respective antibody in blocking buffer and kept at 4 °C
247 overnight. The next day, membrane halves were washed with wash buffer and incubated with
248 goat anti-mouse IgG recombinant secondary antibody, Alexa Fluor 647 (1:2500, Invitrogen,
249 A28181), as well as phalloidin A488 (1:50, Sigma-Aldrich, 49409) and DAPI (1:500; Sigma-
250 Aldrich, D9542), in blocking buffer for one hour at RT. Finally, membranes were washed with
251 wash buffer and ultrapure water and were covered with fluorescence mounting medium (Dako
252 Glycergel, Agilent, C056330-2) on microscope slides. Images were captured with the
253 Lionheart FX automated microscope (magnification given in the figure caption) and processed
254 with the Gen5 Data Analysis Software.

255

256 **2.9 Statistical analysis**

257 The statistical significance was analyzed using one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA)
258 combined with multiple comparisons using the Dunnett's test. The level of significance was
259 set as $p < 0.05$. All experiments were performed in at least three independent experiments. All
260 data were analyzed and illustrated using GraphPad Prism, version 9.0.0 for Windows

261 (GraphPad Software, La Jolla California USA). Statistical significances are marked by
262 asterisks (*: $p < 0.05$, **: $p < 0.01$, ***: $p < 0.001$, ****: $p < 0.0001$).

263

264 **3. Results**

265 **3.1 MWCNTs characterization**

266 Multi-walled carbon nanotubes with size specifications like WHO fibers served as model for
267 fiber toxicity. According to the manufacturer, tubes possess a diameter of 25 nm, an average
268 length of 10-30 μm , and a specific surface area $> 55 \text{ m}^2\text{g}^{-1}$, meeting the criteria of WHO fibers.
269 ScEM imaging of the dry powder showed typical morphology of multi-walled carbon
270 nanotubes (Sos Poulsen et al. 2013) and fiber diameters in accordance to the manufacturer's
271 specifications (**Suppl. Fig. S1**). With a stated purity $> 99.9\%$ a contamination with typical
272 metal catalysts like Ti, Rh, Pt, Pd, Fe or Ni should be excluded, which was confirmed by EDX
273 analysis (**Suppl. Fig. S2**). The DLS measurements of MWCNT suspension in exposure
274 medium of the highest concentration used (50 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$) yielded an average size of 267.7 nm
275 (**Suppl. Fig. S3**), a PDI=0.382 and a ζ -potential of -13.3 mV. The endotoxin content of EC \leq
276 0.004 EU/mL indicated no contamination of bacterial origin.

277

278 **3.2 Cell model establishment**

279 The necessity of an appropriate *in vitro* model closely mimicking physiological conditions as
280 well as predicting pathological outcomes associated with pulmonary fibrosis was highlighted
281 already by previous studies (Clippinger et al. 2016; Barosova, Karakocak, et al. 2020).
282 Following a comparable approach, we were aiming to develop a complex but easy-to-use
283 model involving cell types known to be highly involved in the regulation of pro-fibrotic
284 pathways. A triple culture model comprising human alveolar type II epithelial cells (A549),
285 macrophage precursor cell line (THP-1) and lung fibroblasts (MRC-5) was successfully
286 established. All cell types could be grown in the same DMEM/F12 medium, facilitating
287 convenient handling. In addition, FBS content of the medium was decreased to 5 % (v/v) two
288 passages after thawing, not only making it easier for the cells to adapt to the serum-free
289 exposure medium, but also to reduce the amount of materials originating from animals. The
290 short PMA treatment of THP-1 monocytes with high concentrations, followed by a longer
291 resting period in fresh medium used here for macrophage differentiation, has previously shown
292 to be beneficial for characteristic expression of macrophage markers (Pinto et al. 2021). THP-
293 1 cells were seeded on top of A549 cells reaching a relevant ratio (Stone et al. 1992) of
294 approximately 1:10 on the day of exposure (green, **Fig. 1B, apical**). Successful adherence and
295 differentiation of THP-1 cells was proved by immunostaining with the macrophage-specific
296 marker CD11b (red, **Fig. 1B, apical**). A coating of inserts with collagen facilitated a fast
297 adherence process of fibroblasts (1h) accompanied by a uniform monolayer formation on the
298 downside of the membrane enabling direct cell-cell contact with the apical cell layer (green,
299 **Fig. 1B, basolateral**).

300

301 The identical seeding and treatment process of all model systems allowed a direct comparison
302 of the systems, elucidating how cell-cell communication within the triple culture model affects
303 its cytotoxic, genotoxic and pro-fibrotic response upon MWCNT treatment compared to
304 simpler model systems missing complex cell-cell interaction. The differences between the
305 models will be presented and interpreted in the following sections.

306

307 3.3 Cytotoxic response induced by MWCNTs

308 To investigate cytotoxic effects on the models, live cells were counted after 24 and 48 h
309 exposure. For A549 cells, a decrease of cell viability with increasing concentrations could be
310 observed for all models. Especially, in the mono culture as well as the co-culture MWCNT
311 treatment reduced the cell count of live cells to ~50 % after 48 h exposure. In contrast, the triple
312 culture was not significantly affected, showing a reduction of live cells to 75 % at the highest
313 concentration after 48 h exposure compared to the untreated control (**Fig. 2a**). The cell viability
314 of fibroblasts in the co- or triple culture was not affected by the treatment (**Fig. 2b**).

315

316

317 **Figure 2:** Cell count of a) apical cells in the mono culture (MC, only A549), co-culture (CC,
318 only A549) and triple culture (TC, A549 + THP-1) as well as b) MRC-5 cells in the CC and
319 TC measured by live cell count after 24 and 48 h MWCNT treatment. Results are presented as
320 mean cell count compared to the untreated control (0.0 $\mu\text{g}/\text{cm}^2$) + SEM; n = 3. c) Cytotoxicity
321 in the mono culture (MC), co-culture (CC) and triple culture (TC) measured by the LDH release
322 into the cell culture medium after 24 and 48 h MWCNT treatment. Results are presented as
323 cytotoxicity compared to the positive control (2 % Triton-X, 100 %) + SEM; MC/CC: n=4 and
324 TC: n = 3. d) % Clonogenicity of A549 cells of the mono culture (MC), co-culture (CC) and
325 triple culture (TC) measured by the colony forming efficiency after 24 and 48 h MWCNT
326 treatment. Results are presented as the mean clonogenicity compared to the untreated control
327 (0.0 $\mu\text{g}/\text{cm}^2$) + SEM; MC/CC/TC (24 h): n = 7, MC/CC (48 h): n = 7, TC (48 h): n=6. Statistical

328 significances with respect to the untreated control are marked by asterisks (*: $p < 0.05$, **: $p <$
329 0.01 , ***: $p < 0.001$, ****: $p < 0.0001$).

330

331 The lower cytotoxicity in the triple culture system is in agreement with the concentration of
332 cytosolic lactate dehydrogenase released into apical as well as basolateral cell culture medium
333 upon treatment. An increased LDH concentration is associated with a rupture of the cell
334 membrane, consequently leading to necrotic cell death (Chan et al. 2013). After 24 h treatment,
335 a significant increase to 19 % cytotoxicity was observed in the MC, which could not be detected
336 in the CC or TC. In general, the basal LDH release appeared to be lower in the TC compared
337 to the other models. This effect was even more pronounced after 48 h treatment. The MC
338 displayed a membrane damage of 31 % already in the untreated control cells, increasing
339 significantly to 54 % at the highest MWCNT exposure, whereas the CC and TC showed a basal
340 LDH release of 20 % and 18 %, respectively. In the CC, the LDH concentration was increasing
341 with increasing concentrations, reaching a significantly elevated level of cytotoxicity (30 %)
342 with the highest treatment. An increased cytotoxic response with increasing MWCNT
343 treatment was not detected in the triple culture (**Fig. 2c**).

344 Furthermore, the colony forming efficiency assay was performed, which is commonly used to
345 analyze cell viability upon particle treatment. Advantageously, it is not only giving information
346 on the cytotoxic potential of a material but also on the ability to impact cell (Ponti et al. 2013).
347 The clonogenicity of A549 cells compared to the untreated control was assessed in all models
348 after 24 and 48 h treatment. It can be estimated that the formed colonies are only A549 cells
349 since THP-1 macrophages do not proliferate. After 24 h, lower MWCNT treatment seemed to
350 have increased – even though not significant – clonogenic potential, which is rescinded with
351 higher concentrations, resulting in a significant decrease of clonogenicity at the highest
352 concentrations in all models (MC: 53 %, CC: 60 %, TC: 68 %) and for the TC at $11.2 \mu\text{g}/\text{cm}^2$
353 already (66 %). After 48 h, the CC showed an increased clonogenicity with the lowest MWCNT
354 concentration ($2.2 \mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$), which was entailed by a significant collapse in clonogenicity with
355 higher concentrations. The latter appeared also in the MC and the TC for the two highest
356 concentrations. The maximum treatment with $22.3 \mu\text{g}/\text{cm}^2$ MWCNTs diminished the
357 clonogenicity of the MC to 41 %, the CC to 32 % and the TC in lower extent to 53 % (**Fig. 2d**).
358 The lower impairment of the triple culture model compared to the other models is in accordance
359 to the aforementioned cytotoxicity endpoints.

360

361 **3.4 Effects on inflammation, oxidative stress and (secondary) genotoxicity of MWCNTs**

362 For a more comprehensive understanding of the differences in cytotoxicity between the cell
363 models, we proceeded to investigate the influence of inflammation and oxidative stress on the
364 observed effects. Exposure to MWCNTs has shown to favor the formation of intracellular
365 reactive oxygen species (ROS), accompanied by activation of pro-inflammatory pathways
366 (Moller et al. 2014). In agreement with that, we analyzed the release of the interleukin 8 (IL-
367 8), which is strongly involved in the pro-inflammatory response upon physical or chemical
368 insult (Turner et al. 2014). In general, the IL-8 release from the TC was of hundreds to

369 thousands magnitudes higher compared to those of the MC or CC. After 24 h treatment, the
 370 TC had a basal release of 516 pg/mL, whereas the MC and the CC showed a release of 161
 371 pg/mL and 43 pg/mL, respectively. An increase with increasing concentrations was detected
 372 only for the TC, significant at the highest concentration with 1,659 pg/mL IL-8. Similar effects
 373 could be observed after 48 h treatment, displaying an increase in all models, only showing a
 374 significant effect in the TC at the highest concentration (1,925 pg/mL). The MC and the CC
 375 reached IL-8 concentrations up to 568 pg/mL and 163 pg/mL, respectively. Again, the IL-8
 376 release of the TC showed a higher variance throughout the whole experiment compared to the
 377 other models (Fig. 3a).

378

379

380 **Figure 3:** a) IL-8 release of the mono culture (MC), co-culture (CC) and triple culture (TC)
 381 after 24 and 48 h MWCNT treatment. Results are presented as mean IL-8 [pg/mL] + SEM;
 382 MC/CC: n=5, TC: n=4. b) Oxidative stress in the mono culture (MC), co-culture (CC) and
 383 triple culture (TC) measured by MDA release after 24 and 48 h MWCNT treatment. Results
 384 are presented as mean MDA [ng/mL] + SEM; n=3. DNA damage in the mono culture (MC),
 385 co-culture (CC) and triple culture (TC) after 24 and 48 h MWCNT treatment in c) apical cells
 386 (A549 + THP-1) and d) MRC-5 cells detected by the comet assay. Results are presented as
 387 mean % DNA in tail + SEM; n=3. Statistical significances with respect to the untreated control
 388 are marked by asterisks (*: p < 0.05, **: p < 0.01, ***: p < 0.001, ****: p < 0.0001).

389

390 In recent years many studies found oxidative stress to play a major role in the manifestation of
 391 inflammation and vice versa. Malondialdehyde is a product of oxidative degeneration of fatty
 392 acids and therefore a commonly used marker of lipid peroxidation, which is associated with
 393 cell damage (Wu et al. 2017). Generally, the highest release of MDA was observed in the TC
 394 model with a stable basal release of 19 ng/mL after 24 h and 21 ng/mL after 48 h exposure.
 395 Likewise, the basal release in the CC was only slightly increased from 10 ng/mL to 13 ng/mL.
 396 In contrast, the MC showed a basal release of 8 ng/mL after 24 h, which strongly increased to
 397 20 ng/mL after 48 h. A clear response to the MWCNT treatment could be observed especially
 398 in the MC and the TC, which rose to 29 ng/mL and 31 ng/mL, respectively. Over all,

399 significance was only shown for the MC, since the TC exhibited a higher variance throughout
400 the whole experiment. Moreover, a minor but significant increase of MDA release up to 15
401 ng/mL could be detected for the CC after 48 h exposure (**Fig. 3b**).

402 As previous studies already highlighted (Rahman et al. 2017; Di Ianni et al. 2021), both
403 oxidative stress as well as inflammation seem to be related to DNA damage caused by multi-
404 walled carbon nanotubes. Assessing the genotoxic potential of MWCNTs, we applied the
405 comet assay, which is commonly used to analyze DNA damage resulting from nanomaterials
406 (Karlsson et al. 2015). The comet assay is able to detect DNA single and double strand breaks
407 as well as alkaline labile sites. The analysis investigated genotoxic effects on the apical cells
408 directly interacting with the material, as well as secondary effects on MRC-5 cells, which were
409 not in direct contact with MWCNTs. It is estimated that after washing, A549 cells are
410 predominantly present. Furthermore, a visual distinction of the cell types can be made during
411 the evaluation based on the different size of the nucleoids. Hence, in A549 cells, generally, a
412 much lower spontaneous DNA damage could be observed in the TC (2.1 % (24 h), 3.1 % (48
413 h)) compared to the MC (6.5 % (24 h), 6.2 % (48 h)) and the CC (6.0 % (24 h), 6.2 % (48 h)).
414 There was no significant increase detected for all models, even though a slight increase in DNA
415 damage was noticed in the MC after 24 h at a concentration of 11.2 $\mu\text{g}/\text{cm}^2$ (7.9 %) and after
416 48 h for 22.3 $\mu\text{g}/\text{cm}^2$ (7.9 %). For the TC, an increase with increasing concentrations after 48
417 h up to 5.1 % DNA damage following the highest treatment could be detected (**Fig. 3c**). In
418 MRC-5 cells, a similar trend regarding lower spontaneous DNA damage of the TC (3.9 % (24
419 h), 3.8 % (48 h)) compared to the CC (4.5 % (24 h), 5.9 % (48 h)) was found. After 24 h
420 treatment, a non-significant increase in DNA damage could be detected in the CC reaching a
421 level of 6.8 % DNA damage with the highest concentration (22.3 $\mu\text{g}/\text{cm}^2$). Moreover, a clear
422 significant increase in secondary genotoxicity could be observed after 48 h exposure in the TC
423 (5.5 %). In contrast to the aforementioned observations, the TC showed a lower variance in
424 between replicates in both cell types throughout the whole experiment compared to the other
425 models (**Fig. 3d**).

426

427 **3.5 Fibrotic response induced by MWCNTs**

428 As already known from asbestos fibers (Gaensler et al. 1991), a key event in fiber associated
429 lung pathology is fibrosis. The latter manifests itself when wound repair processes are impaired
430 and is associated with an irreversible remodeling of the alveolar epithelium undergoing
431 epithelial-mesenchymal transition (EMT) as well as an activation of fibroblasts and
432 differentiation into myofibroblasts (Vietti et al. 2016). A commonly used marker to study
433 fibrosis induction is the increased expression of TGF- β (Meng et al. 2016). This study revealed
434 that, in general, the MC displays a much lower basal level of TGF- β release into the cell culture
435 medium with 112 pg/mL after 24 h and 154 pg/mL after 48 h compared to the CC and TC with
436 447 pg/mL and 354 pg/mL after 24 h and 660 pg/mL and 560 pg/mL after 48 h, respectively.
437 After 48 h, in all models the TGF- β levels are slightly accelerated. Both the MC (201 pg/mL)
438 and CC (750 pg/mL) showed a slight increase in release after 48 h, but none of the models
439 revealed a clear significant increase in TGF- β release compared to the respective negative
440 control, neither after 24 h nor 48 h of MWCNT treatment (**Fig. 4A**).

442

443 **Figure 4:** A) TGF- β release of the mono culture (MC), co-culture (CC) and triple culture (TC)
 444 after 24 and 48 h MWCNT treatment. Results are presented as mean TGF- β [pg/mL] + SEM;
 445 MC/CC: n=5, TC: n=4. Statistical significances with respect to the untreated control are
 446 marked by asterisks (*: $p < 0.05$, **: $p < 0.01$, ***: $p < 0.001$, ****: $p < 0.0001$). B)
 447 Morphology of the apical side of the mono culture (MC), co-culture (CC) and triple culture
 448 (TC) after 48 h treatment with 22.3 $\mu\text{g}/\text{cm}^2$ MWCNTs and untreated control cells (Ctrl). Actin
 449 staining with phalloidin A488 (green) + nuclei staining with DAPI (blue). Scale bar, 100 μm .

450

451 Even though no clear indication for the development of a fibrotic milieu was given by the TGF- β
 452 analysis, we had a closer look on the cell morphology after 48 h treatment with the highest

453 concentration of 22.3 μg MWCNTs/cm². The latter showed the strongest effects in the
454 cytotoxicity as well as the MDA and IL-8 assessment for all models. In the microscopic
455 analysis, the MC exhibited a clear disruption of the epithelial cell layer including a loss of
456 membrane integrity and cell death indicated by small, round nuclei with a bright DAPI staining
457 (blue, **Fig. 4B**). In contrast, the CC and TC still displayed a uniform cell layer after the
458 treatment, nevertheless showing a reorganization of actin structures by losing the cuboidal cell
459 shape as seen in the negative control towards a mesenchymal-like spindle shape (green, **Fig.**
460 **4B**). This depolarization effect was much more pronounced in the TC and could be observed
461 as an elongation and stretching of the cell body as well as the nucleus accompanied by the
462 formation of actin stress fibers. In addition to that, a change in morphology of the TC compared
463 to the other models could be observed already in the untreated control.

464 The strong indication of a pro-fibrotic response of the TC by the morphological assessment,
465 initiated an immunohistochemical investigation of fibrosis-associated markers (Loh et al.
466 2019) on the apical side of all cell models (**Fig. 5**). This analysis revealed a downregulation of
467 epithelial cadherin (E-cadherin) expression in MWCNT treated epithelial cells of the CC and
468 TC model systems. For the TC, also after 48 h treatment, even though in a reduced form, an E-
469 cadherin expression was detected. In contrast, the MC seemed to express only low levels of E-
470 cadherin before and after treatment, displaying no clear regulation. Furthermore, an
471 upregulation of neural cadherin (N-cadherin) expression upon MWCNT exposure was noticed
472 in all models and seemed to be expressed highest in the TC. This cadherin transition implicates
473 a reorganization of cell-cell adhesion, allowing cells to migrate and is strongly associated with
474 EMT.

475

476

477 **Figure 5:** Antibody staining (AB) of the apical side of the mono culture (MC), co-culture (CC)
 478 and triple culture (TC) after 48 h treatment with 22.3 $\mu\text{g}/\text{cm}^2$ MWCNTs and untreated control
 479 cells (Ctrl). E-cadherin and N-cadherin staining with Alexa Fluor 647 (red) + nuclei staining
 480 with DAPI (blue). Scale bar, 100 μm .

481

482 In addition, commonly used markers for pulmonary fibrosis are the vimentin and α -smooth
 483 muscle actin (α -SMA) expression in lung fibroblasts (Ohbayashi et al. 2014). The CC as well
 484 as TC showed an increased expression of both markers after 48 h treatment with MWCNTs
 485 compared to the untreated control (**Fig. 6**).

486

487

488 **Figure 6:** Antibody staining (AB) of the basolateral side of the co-culture (CC) and triple
 489 culture (TC) after 48 h treatment with 22.3 $\mu\text{g}/\text{cm}^2$ MWCNTs and untreated control cells (Ctrl).
 490 Vimentin and α -smooth muscle actin (α -SMA) staining with Alexa Fluor 647 (red) + nuclei
 491 staining with DAPI (blue). Scale bar, 100 μm .

492

493 4. Discussion

494 From the beginning of industrialization and the onset of heavy urban traffic, but also due to
 495 climate change (Schweitzer et al. 2018), we are increasingly exposed to airborne particles, such
 496 as fibers (e.g. asbestos, carbon nanotubes), dust particles (e.g. SiO_2), fine particulate matter
 497 ($\text{PM}_{2.5}$) or ultrafine particulate matter ($\text{PM}_{0.1}$). This makes an all-encompassing toxicological
 498 analysis of such pollutants indispensable. Since science faces ethical and technical hurdles
 499 regarding the characterization of respiratory health risks in humans, the development of
 500 alternative test systems is necessary to model the human organism. Moreover, the use of
 501 animals is not ethically justifiable and does exhibit major drawbacks due to, for example,
 502 different respiratory tract anatomy, breathing patterns and clearance as well as compound
 503 elimination mechanisms of different species (Mowat et al. 2017). Alternative strategies
 504 comprise particle deposition and clearance being mathematically modeled and *in vitro* test
 505 systems developed to determine the toxicity of environmental aerosols at an early stage to
 506 establish initial indications of their behavior in the pulmonary system. Awareness regarding
 507 the 3R concept (reduction, replacement and refinement of animal experiments) has increased

508 and many *in vitro* models have been developed in recent years to address acute inhalation
509 toxicology in particular (Klein et al. 2013; Sauer et al. 2013; Barosova, Karakocak, et al. 2020;
510 Offer et al. 2022). However, there are limited studies involving complex test systems, which
511 are able to represent and link specific key events associated with the formation of pulmonary
512 fibrosis of alveolar regions. These systems might be used to derive mechanistic linkage of
513 molecular key events in the frame of an adverse outcome pathway leading to improved
514 regulatory application (Halappanavar et al. 2020). Few studies exist that use a similar triple
515 culture model as in our study, but they do not address fibrosis-associated changes in sufficient
516 detail (Barosova, Karakocak, et al. 2020). Other studies use co-cultures with fibroblasts seeded
517 at the bottom of the well only allowing indirect contact through the culture medium and no
518 direct interaction with other cell types (Waghray et al. 2005; Di Ianni et al. 2021). In this
519 context, the commercially available EpiAlveolar™ microtissue model (MatTek, USA) should
520 be mentioned, which contains both alveolar epithelial cells and fibroblasts. It is also available
521 with macrophages, but they are cultured together with the other cell types in one compartment
522 (Barosova, Maione, et al. 2020). Therefore, more advanced techniques are needed to perform
523 mechanistic studies regarding secondary effects on a single cell type since cell types need to
524 be separated beforehand. Additionally, the SMALLAIR™-HF model (Epithelix, Switzerland)
525 is commercially available and comprises small airway epithelial cells as well as fibroblasts at
526 distinct sites of the membrane, but does not consider immune cell interaction, which might not
527 reflect the alveolar microenvironment sufficiently. Even though these models are ready-to-use
528 and may be available with patient-derived tissue, they are cost-intensive, especially when used
529 in a larger scale. In contrast, the triple culture model we use can be established in any laboratory
530 without great expense, is easy to reproduce and to adjust. All cell types used are easily
531 accessible and grow in the same cell culture medium, which was the reason for not choosing
532 primary cells like e.g. human Alveolar Epithelial Lentivirus immortalized (hAELVi) cells,
533 which express tight junctions but are more time-consuming to grow and need a more advanced
534 cell culture medium (Kuehn et al. 2016). In addition to that, our model allows intracellular
535 mechanistic studies, such as secondary genotoxicity on fibroblasts without the need of any
536 advanced cell separation techniques. Moreover, all materials of animal origin used in the model
537 (collagen I, FBS, trypsin, antibodies) could be – and should be in future projects – replaced by
538 non-animal products (e.g. synthetic coating, serum-free media, recombinant trypsin and
539 recombinant antibodies). Within our means, we reduced animal products in this study as much
540 as possible by decreasing the serum content (Chary et al. 2022) in cell culture and by starting
541 to buy synthetic recombinant antibodies.

542 In addition to the ethical, practical and financial advantages, the developed model (TC) exhibits
543 significant differences from simpler models (MC or CC) in terms of biological response upon
544 exposure to the used MWCNTs (**Fig. 7**). No necrotic cell death in the form of LDH release was
545 observed in the TC, which however was detected to a higher extent in the MC and to a lesser
546 extent in the CC. The reduced effect seen in the TC is analogous to a previous study of
547 Barosova et al., 2020 (Barosova, Karakocak, et al. 2020) investigating cytotoxic effects of
548 possibly carcinogenic (IARC group 2B) Mitsui-7 MWCNTs (Mitsui-7) in a similar triple
549 culture system. These low necrotic effects could be attributed to a protective response of the
550 alveolar macrophages (Bowden 1984), which might surround the fibrous material and thereby

551 prevent direct contact of the material with epithelial cells as it is the case in the MC. This is in
552 agreement with an *in vitro* study analyzing the cell uptake of Mitsui-7 in mono cultures of
553 macrophages, epithelial cells as well as fibroblast, which shows that MWCNTs are internalized
554 by all cell types but most rapidly by macrophages (Chortarea 2019). Furthermore, an animal
555 study, in which mice were exposed to Mitsui-7, showed a cell uptake of material mainly in
556 alveolar macrophages (~ 70 %) compared to epithelial cells (~ 8 %) showing reduced direct
557 contact of epithelial cells with MWCNTs when macrophages are present (Mercer et al. 2011).
558 In the MC, the fibers may directly exert physical stress on the cells, MWCNTs could be
559 internalized (Chortarea 2019) and accumulate with increasing concentrations and exposure
560 duration inside the cell (Srivastava et al. 2011) resulting in a higher cytotoxicity compared to
561 the multiple cell type cultures. Previous studies with Mitsui-7 using a similar concentration
562 range showed comparable effects in the MTT assay in A549 mono cultures after 24 h and 48 h
563 submerged exposure. Furthermore, they observed a protective effect of macrophages in a
564 system comprising differentiated THP-1 and A549 cells after 48 h exposure (MTT assay and
565 Caspase 3/7 activity), which might be related to the inflammatory response of the immune cells
566 indicated by a stronger release of the pro-inflammatory cytokine IL-1 β by the THP-1 cell
567 containing model compared to the mono culture (Ventura et al. 2020). The lower necrotic
568 cytotoxicity in the higher concentrations observed in the CC could have been caused by
569 induced fibroblast signaling. It has already been shown that pathological fibroblasts in
570 idiopathic pulmonary fibrosis (IPF) promote a pro-apoptotic milieu and favor apoptotic cell
571 death of epithelial cells (Uhal et al. 1995; Wang R et al. 1999; Barbas-Filho et al. 2001). This
572 observation is congruent with the results of the colony forming efficiency assay, which showed
573 the lowest clonogenicity in the CC compared to the other models, thus implying an increased
574 apoptotic response or impaired clonogenicity. Also in the TC the clonogenic potential was
575 affected, even if to a lower extent than in the other systems. Although the two simpler models
576 display different pathways of cell death, cytotoxicity is reflected to a similar extent in the live
577 cell count. Consistent with the previous endpoints, also the TC exhibited a reduction in cell
578 number, which appears to be predominantly due to apoptosis, according to the results of the
579 LDH and the CFE assay, but seems to be less affected overall.

580 In contrast, a high concentration of IL-8 was detected in the triple culture, which increased with
581 increasing duration and increased MWCNT concentrations. These findings are in line with
582 previous studies, which have shown already that co-cultures including epithelial cells as well
583 as macrophages react more sensitive to particle exposure compared to epithelial mono cultures
584 (Wottrich et al. 2004; Meindl et al. 2021). This observation could be explained by the fact that
585 residential alveolar macrophages not only are the first to be in direct contact with the material
586 and are able to release IL-8 to a great extent, but also induce the IL-8 production of epithelial
587 cell to increase chemotactic signaling (Kunkel et al. 1991; Thorley et al. 2007). In particular,
588 in response to the removal of contaminants and tissue damage, it is known, that macrophages
589 are involved in the release of inflammatory cytokines like IL-8 in order to recruit other immune
590 cells like neutrophils to the site of action to enhance tissue defense and repair (Carre et al. 1991;
591 Di Ianni et al. 2021). Increased IL-8 levels and the infiltration of neutrophils is strongly
592 associated with IPF and seems to be negatively correlated with lung function. Accordingly, the
593 level of IL-8 is used as biomarker in IPF to determine the degree of disease progression

594 (Ziegenhagen et al. 1998; Tsoutsou et al. 2006). The fibroblasts in the CC on the other hand
595 seem to favor an anti-inflammatory milieu attenuating the levels of IL-8. An increased
596 production of pro-apoptotic biomarkers (Uhal et al. 1998), which often leads to an anti-
597 inflammatory response (Juncadella et al. 2013; Szondy et al. 2017), as well as an
598 immunomodulatory potential could be observed in diseased fibroblasts as well as
599 myofibroblasts (Chavez-Galan et al. 2022). As seen in the comet assay, fibroblasts seemed to
600 be altered already during the 24 h exposure, which could be related to the aberrant IL-8
601 signaling. Furthermore, already control cells after 48 h exposure showed a myofibroblasts-like
602 vimentin expression indicating an abnormal differentiation of fibroblasts. The slight induction
603 of IL-8 in the MC might be mediated by oxidative stress, which could be directly increased by
604 reactive oxygen species (ROS) released from ruptured lysosomes (Stern et al. 2012; Hussain
605 et al. 2014). This release is reflected in the MDA levels, which were elevated in the MC and
606 increased with increasing concentrations. Moreover, IL-8 is known to favor respiratory burst
607 (Pilette et al. 2002; Brechard et al. 2005), increasing the release of ROS and enhancing lipid
608 peroxidation (Kwiatkowska et al. 1999; Herb and Schramm 2021). This interaction might
609 explain the increasing concentrations of MDA detected with increasing concentrations of
610 MWCNTs in the TC and the comparably low levels observed in the CC.

611 Not only oxidative stress, but also increased IL-8 levels are associated with DNA damage (Di
612 Ianni et al. 2021), which was detected in the TC after 48 h treatment in epithelial cells (not
613 significant), but especially as indirect secondary effect in lung fibroblasts (significant). Similar
614 primary effects could be detected *in vivo* as well as *in vitro* for the reference particle Mitsui-7
615 as summarized by Møller et al., 2021 (Moller et al. 2021), but, to the best of our knowledge,
616 this study is the first to detect secondary genotoxicity of MWCNTs on fibroblast cells. A
617 manifestation of DNA mutations occurring due to increased oxidative damage or impaired
618 DNA damage repair mechanisms could explain the altered function of lung fibroblasts in
619 wound healing processes and the subsequent fibrotic progression. This process might correlate
620 with the senescence of fibroblasts as well as myofibroblasts strongly featured in IPF-derived
621 fibroblasts (Yanai et al. 2015; Arish et al. 2019; Parimon et al. 2021). In addition to that, we
622 observed considerable lower levels of spontaneous DNA damage in the triple culture compared
623 to the other models, which seem to appear due to the complex microenvironment regulated by
624 immune cells and epithelial cells. This observation could be explained by a deceleration of the
625 cell cycle by macrophages, which are able to coordinate the cell cycle of epithelial cells
626 (Mussar et al. 2014) possibly enabling enhanced DNA repair. Considering, that humans show
627 lower levels of endogenous oxidative DNA lesions per day than rats (Helbock et al. 1998) or
628 mice (Foksinski et al. 2004), the observed effects in the triple culture might resemble human
629 physiological conditions even better than the other models.

630

631

632 **Figure 7:** Overview of all endpoints after 24 h and 48 h exposure to MWCNTs of different
 633 concentrations (2.2, 4.5, 11.2, 22.3 $\mu\text{g}/\text{cm}^2$) in the respective cell models represented as fold
 634 change (FC) compared to the respective negative control after 24 or 48 h.

635

636 The changes in cell cycle could furthermore explain the altered morphology of epithelial cells
 637 in the untreated control of the triple culture compared to the other cell systems as the shape of
 638 cells is known to change throughout the cell cycle (e.g. volume, surface area) depending on the
 639 phase (Clark and Paluch 2011). In addition to that, there are clear differences in response to the
 640 treatment with MWCNTs for 48 h by the TC compared to the other system when assessing
 641 morphological changes. In the mono culture, a disrupted cell layer is seen with loss of
 642 membrane integrity and numerous dead cells. The latter is not observed in the co-culture, but
 643 epithelial cells lose their cuboidal structure and dilate. This structural change is also found in
 644 the triple culture, albeit to an increased extent. In this model, epithelial cells have acquired a
 645 spindle-like shape and formed so-called actin stress fibers, which are typical for EMT and could
 646 also be detected in bronchial epithelial cells treated with MWCNTs physicochemically similar
 647 to Mitsui-7 (Polimeni et al. 2016). The morphological alteration is also reflected in the protein
 648 expression of E- and N-cadherin in the triple culture. There, a downregulation of E- and an
 649 upregulation of N-cadherin is clearly seen after prolonged treatment with MWCNTs. E-
 650 cadherin is crucial to grant the epithelial phenotype and is reversibly switched to N-cadherin
 651 in homeostatic wound healing processes or permanently in persistent pathological changes.
 652 This shift can also be observed in the co-culture model, but not in the mono culture, which

653 lacked E-cadherin expression under these conditions. A stronger downregulation of E-cadherin
654 was observed after 48 h exposure to Mitsui-7 in a co-culture of A549 and THP-1 cells compared
655 to a mono culture of A549 cells (Ventura et al. 2020). The change in morphology allows the
656 cell to break away from the structural association within the cell layer and migrate to the site
657 of injury to promote wound healing (Thiery et al. 2009). *In vivo* as well as *in vitro* it was shown
658 that especially long MWCNTs are prone to induce a pro-fibrotic environment via EMT
659 mechanisms (Chen et al. 2014; Wang P et al. 2015; Polimeni et al. 2016). The transformation
660 of epithelial cells to mesenchymal cells (Yao et al. 2019) and the release of growth factors by
661 macrophages (He et al. 2011) are estimated to play an important role in the pathogenesis of
662 pulmonary fibrosis by activating fibroblasts through paracrine signaling and enhancing a pro-
663 fibrotic environment. This activation could be observed in the co- as well as the triple culture
664 by assessing fibroblast-to-myofibroblasts-associated biomarkers like alpha smooth muscle
665 actin as well as vimentin, which are strongly upregulated in myofibroblasts of fibrotic diseases
666 (Chen et al. 2014; Wang P et al. 2015). The same effect was detected in the co- as well as the
667 triple culture model, even though the vimentin expression seemed to be stronger in the co-
668 culture, which indicates myofibroblasts at a progressed diseased stage, explaining the
669 promotion of a pro-apoptotic microenvironment of epithelial cells, without taking into
670 consideration the pro-inflammatory effects of macrophages.

671

672 **5. Conclusion**

673 Previous knowledge of underlying mechanisms of fibrosis and toxicity classifications were
674 mainly obtained from animal experiments, which could be reduced in the future by applying
675 more advanced cell culture models. The developed triple culture is able to detect cytotoxicity,
676 genotoxicity and fibrotic alterations not only of epithelial cells but also of fibroblasts, taking
677 into account the interplay of the most important cell types playing a major role in pulmonary
678 fibrotic diseases. The gained results indicate that the TC is able to reflect initial protective
679 mechanisms known from *in vivo* studies to greater extent than simpler cell models. In
680 particular, the fact that macrophages play a crucial role with respect to the defense mechanisms
681 of the lung and thus in the removal of harmful materials is taken into consideration in the more
682 complex *in vitro* test system. In addition, the model is able to identify intermediate pro-fibrotic
683 key events such as DNA damage, morphological changes and fibrotic biomarkers that may
684 indicate a potential adverse outcome. This study has shown that MWCNTs with WHO
685 dimensions induce secondary genotoxicity in fibroblasts, especially after prolonged exposure,
686 and cause EMT-associated morphological and structural changes in epithelial cells and
687 fibroblasts of the triple culture. These effects seem to be strongly correlated with increased IL-
688 8 levels and ROS production and are related to the complex microenvironment formed by the
689 different cell types. In future studies, the TC cell system should be used at the air-liquid-
690 interface (ALI), which will reflect the physiology of the human respiratory tract even closer
691 and allows a more realistic toxicological characterization of potentially fibrotic materials. Even
692 though the developed model shows big advantages in contrast to less complex systems,
693 prospective studies should furthermore involve the development of a cell model using epithelial

694 cells able to express tight junctions, which are thereby more suited for conducting EMT studies
695 and subsequent analysis of fibrotic outcomes.

696

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916

917 **Data availability statement**

918 The data that support the findings of this study are available from the corresponding author,
919 upon request.

920

921 **Disclosure Statement**

922 The authors declare that they have no conflicts of interest.

923

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943

944 **Supplementary Material**

945

946

947 **Figure S1:** Field emission scanning electron microscope (ScEM) of the purchased dry
948 MWCNT powder in 10,000× magnification (left) and 75,000× magnification (right).

949

950

951 **Figure S2:** Elements found on MWCNT bulk particles surface measured with ScEM-EDX at
952 2084× magnification. S: Sulfur, C: Carbon, O: Oxygen, Na: Sodium, Si: Silica.

953

	Size (d.nm):	% Intensity:	St Dev (d.n...)
Z-Average (d.nm): 267,7	Peak 1: 374,5	90,1	366,0
Pdl: 0,382	Peak 2: 4274	9,9	1054
Intercept: 0,882	Peak 3: 0,000	0,0	0,000

Result quality : Good

954

955 **Figure S3:** DLS measurements of MWCNT suspension in exposure medium of the highest
956 concentration used (50 µg/mL).

957